

An Investigation into Occupational Stress and Job Performance in the Employees of Mobile Phone Companies

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Abstract:

Stress is a widespread factor and persons in every walk of life have to face it. The employees working in different organizations have to deal with stress. Especially Mobile phone Companies are under a great deal of stress due to many previous circumstances of stress. These stresses supply to decrease managerial routine, decreased employee by and large performance, decreased excellence of job, high staff proceeds, and absence due to health problems such as apprehension, misery, annoyance and back pain. Six components of job stress: Lack of administrative support, excessive work demand, problematic customer relations, coworker's relationship, family & work life balance and riskiness of job were examined in this study. The purpose of the study is to investigate the stress interrelated problems of Mobile phone Companies and examine the relationship between stress and performance. And finally the impact of stress on employee performance. For this purpose 140 questionnaires were filled by Mobile phone Companies employees Jazz, Telenor, Ufone, Mobilink, Zong and Warid. The results show that all the components of stress cause great stress in Mobile companies and then diminish their routine.

Key words: Job Performance, Mobile Phone Companies, Stress.

Introduction

This is an age of science and technology; a lot of inventions are taken place by different people of different fields. Due to technology improvements now we are gaining a lot of facilities but with these facilities we are facing a lot of problems in our day to day life. There are many factors that affect the health of a man such as pollution, water born disease, pornography, credit card fraud, lack of face to face communication, mental stress problems, congestion and being too materialistic and competitive are the gifts of modern science and technology. But in this paper only the affects of stress are discussing on the performance of teachers of private schools in Pakistan.

Stress has been defined by (Kaila, 2005), as follows: “an adaptive reaction, mediated by entity differences and/ or psychosomatic processes, that is outcome of any peripheral (ecological) act, state, or occasion that places extreme emotional and/ or physical anxiety upon an individual.”

The operational surroundings of the business organizations in the service area have evolved severely. In a number of high get in touch with service organizations, patrons classically come up to the service providers (i.e. real estate industry, lawful services, beauty salons) at the same time as in other areas, the service organizations start the get in touch with (i.e. Insurance, shares market agents(Ismail, 2011).

The sympathy industry is characterized by extensive working hours; repeatedly behind schedule at night and very early sunrise reporting. A lot of the work requires workers to be continually on their feet and purchaser interactions can be stressful, as workers may be vocally ill-treated for service problems that are not any of their liability and fully out of their be in command of. In addition, a lot of of them have problems maintaining a work-life equilibrium. These factors individually or in combination lead to ill-health, low morale, conflicts and high levels of stress. In an effort to help employees cope with such issues, organizations have invested in workplace recreation(Samuel Obino Mokaya, 2012)

suitable place of work circumstances are necessities for improving output and excellence of outcomes, operational circumstances in a lot of organizations may present be short of of security, health and console issues such as shocking lightening and aeration, extreme sound and crisis surplus(Leblebici D. , 2012).

The persistent obligation to work at most favorable recital takes its toll in job discontent, employee income, condensed competence, sickness and even death. Absenteeism, ill health, alcoholism, "insignificant interior politics", awful or crack decisions, unresponsiveness and lack of concern, lack of inspiration or originality are all by-products of an over harassed place of work(MANJULA, 2007).

Causes of employment strain have been connected to the labor itself, e.g. growing anxiety, less autonomy to be in charge of one's work, and also to the self, e.g. inadequate aptitude to deal with time pressures, etc(Houtman, 2007).

It is the liability of administration to scrap against the stress at work, to spot the appropriate route of action and resolve them. Improving stress avoidance is an optimistic action that contributes to a improved physical condition of personnel and generates vast organization competence and presentation (Rahim, 2010).

Stress causes non-attendance and can guide to other troubles such as drug habit, alcoholism, gloominess, and deprived work performance.

There are many bodily as well as touching responses comprise recurrent headaches, jaw clenching or hurt, complexity absorbed, racing belief, absentmindedness, incompetence, confusion, chilly or perspiring hands, feet, small attention in exterior, promptness, thoughts of loneliness or insignificance, amplified smoking, alcohol or drug use, misery, recurrent or untamed frame of mind swings and many other harms upset the performance of recruits(AIS, 2012)

Performance criteria are standards for employee behavior at work. This criterion contains much more than how an employee does the work.

Literature Review

Some factors in administrative center location may be measured keys upsetting employee's appointment, output, confidence, soothe height etc. Both absolutely and harmfully. even though suitable bureau circumstances are necessities for civilizing efficiency and excellence of outcomes, working situation in numerous organizations may in attendance be short of of protection, health and reassure issues such as rude lightening and airing, extreme sound and crisis surplus(Leblebici, 2012).

It is the mental and physical state that consequences when the possessions of the entity are not enough to manage with the strain and pressures of the circumstances. Thus, stress is more probable in some situations than others and in some persons than others. Stress can weaken the attainment of goals, both for individuals and for organizations(S Michie, 2002).

Sensation as if you have no is in charge of in excess of your work or job duties is the largest cause of [job stress](#), captivating on supplementary duties in your job is traumatic. Emotion unconfident concerning the job performance is a main foundation of stress for a lot of people. Hesitation about work roles. Being uncertain about your duties, how your job might be varying, or the goals of your region or corporation can lead to stress. Anxiety on the job frequently comes from deprived communication. Lack of support from your superior or co-worker makes it harder to resolve other troubles at vocation that are causing stress. Repulsive or unsafe physical circumstances, such as crowding, sound or [ergonomic](#) harms, can [cause stress](#) (WebMD, 2009).

Exhaustion and work too hard: This kind of stress builds up more a long time and takes a tough excise. It can be caused by working besides a large amount or moreover unbreakable at jobs or habitat. It can also cause by not significant how to supervise the instance fine and receive moment for rest and take a break. There are countless causes of stress in life like bereavement, ill vigor fatality of misdeed, self violence, family transform, sexual harms dispute, corporal change, moving to new spot, fiscal disaster, surroundings and augment in dependability(MANJULA, 2007).

Workplace stress is the reply people may practice when obtainable with work stress and pressures that are not coordinated to their information and abilities and which confront their aptitude to handle. It has been described as an affecting knowledge linked with anxiety, worry and damage, brought concerning by factors connected to work place of work pressure is a anxiety for together workers and employers, with nationwide and global statistics showing the occurrence has full-grown progressively over new years(Medibank, 2008).

This judgment is that stress and discontent were linked with be short of of time, lack of advice on efficiency, day to day bureaucracy and lack of managerial support and be deficient in of consultation in relation to organizational matters (Warren, 2007).

Most infrastructure tools operators, such as telephone operators, work at video exhibit terminals in lovely, well-lighted, air-conditioned environments. The speedy velocity of the profession and close up regulation may cause stress. Some workplaces have introduced inventive practices in the middle of their operators to decrease work-related stress (Junior, 2008).

Locus of control refers to the causes that folk's characteristic the outcomes, their successes and failures to them. The causes or motivators may be interior and exterior. Thus, inner motivators refer to the craving of job fulfillment, self-worth, and excellence of life in truth they are individual or inside motivators that the people themselves should strengthen them to add to their manage and latitude above stressors. In difference, outdoor motivators are better jobs, promotions and higher earnings that can be provided by supervisors, managers and organizations to give confidence the staff to endorse their recital in their organizations(Karimi, 2011).

Work stress is consideration to influence organizations by rising malingering, declining obligation to work, escalating staff earnings, impairing performance and efficiency, increasing dangerous operational practices and mishap rates, growing legal responsibility to permissible claims and events by stressed workers, damaging the organization's likeness both among its personnel and outwardly (Leka, 2003).

The fundamental resource of the stress frequently is credited to managerial evils such as uncertain guidelines, insufficient communication, contradictory instructions, lack of occasion to contribute in managerial unsuitable parameter, and the like. In actually, be short of of directorial hold up ranked amongst the sources of stress in all three states incorporated in a state learning of correctional bureaucrat stress(Jeanne B, 2011).

One of the predictable penalties of work overload, particularly the quantitative excess that consequences from employment downsizing, is rising time force. While work burden and time pressure may split some ordinary discrepancy as sources of stress for executives, they all have split inconsistency as well(Perrewe, 2004).

Practical measures which organization can take on to run stress as follows: Setting obvious objectives – this helps to reduce job and role vagueness. Conducting stress review – this is an efficient hands-on deed to battle stress particularly in the midst of executives. It involves an effort by the organization to study, travel around, and manage a variety of types of stress which the person executives may practice in the course of the theater their roles. civilizing human being – occupation fit – by maximize human being job fit from side to side cautious showing, assortment and assignment of workers, organizations can assuage a great pact of stress(Salami, 2010).

Many of us use a great part of our instance working with the same cluster of people. When we like these people and take pleasure in effective with them, our work can be intensely pleasing and we can attain a great contract. But if we discover our co-workers complicated to deal with and cooperation is swamped with clash, work rapidly becomes stressful and horrid. Disagreement inside our teams can badly weaken our efficiency and in the end, the achievement of our effort.

Researchers studying the effects of stress on decision-making found that anxiety changes the way people weigh risks and rewards.

A new study on how stress affects one's decision making warns people from making vital choices while beneath stress; as the majority of the time it is have to to leave incorrect. Sentiment upset affects how people consider risk and recompense, as a stressful mind is added disposed towards considering optimistic side of any state. The most recent research is rather opposing to the universal conviction which connections nervousness and stress with lack of enthusiasm and ill energy (Thaman, 2012).

Bad relations with your co-workers can cause marvelous stress, as can working in dysfunctional teams. A lack of interpersonal sustain or poor working associations primary to a logic of separation. People being asked to do a work for which they contain inadequate knowledge or preparation. Complexity settling into a new endorsement, both in circumstances of assembly the new role's necessities and adapting to likely changes in associations with generation(HSE, 2009).

So, the rest of the family is reliant on him. For some or other cause if he loses his job, the family succumbs to the complete financial disaster. Therefore, the responsible male associate forever needs to take the heaviness of this kind of 'possible joblessness'. Not only the person anxious is under stress, but it also has its telling consequence on the additional members of the family. The cause is obvious, because monetary constancy ensures the prospect and happiness of the family (SINHA, 2012).

Job lack of confidence causing stress or dissatisfaction, which in turns increases (or decreases) competence(Farrell, 2005). Physical stress occurs when the human body is exaggerated by sleep deficiency, overworking, extreme physical action, physical wrong or pain, viral or bacterial infections, irritation, physical sickness or unceasing soreness (Jeffrey A. Kottler, 2011).

Methodology:

Dependent variable is employee performance, job stress has been taken as independent variable while Work overload & time pressure, lack of administrative support, coworker's relationship, family & work life balance, problematic customer relations, riskiness of job and excessive work demand have been taken as moderating variables. The most important rationale of the study is to find out the factors caucuses' job stress and the correlation

among job stress and employee performance. Mobile companies employees in this study refer to Branch level Managers, operational managers, supervisors and officers. To achieve the objectives of the study 135 surveys were sent (through questioners) to 6 larger companies having branches in allover Pakistan. For this purpose 140 questionnaires were filled by Mobile phone Companies employees Jazz, Telenor, Ufone, Mobilink, Zong and Warid). And all the mobile companies are listed at Karachi stock exchange of Pakistan. All the workers were matured among 20 to 60 years. Therefore 128 questionnaires were returned having reply rate of 94.8%. The questionnaire using 5-Scale Liker (1=Highly Agreed 2=Agreed, 3=somehow Agreed, 4=Disagreed, 5=Highly Disagreed) was planned to check the impact of all the variables. For this study the questionnaire is divided into 2 sections demographics and job stress & its impact on employee concert. The questionnaire coat all the variables such as lack of administrative support, excessive work demand, problematic customer relations, coworker's relationship, family & work life balance and riskiness of job. The data was analyzed through SPSS v.19.

Sample Characteristics:

The Tables below summarize the respondents' characteristics according to their gender, age, qualification, working positions, experience and income. Male employees made the healthy proportion of the sample size. About 66.40 % of the respondents were under 30 years of age. 57.30 % of respondents having Master's degree. 12.5% respondents were branch level managers, 19.53% manager operations, 32.81% were supervisors and 35.16% were officers, majority of which has income range from Rs.41,000 to Rs. 60,000. All the respondents were taken from branch level operations. .

Table I: Respondent's gender.

	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Male	85	66.40	66.40
Female	43	33.60	100
	128	100	

Table II: Respondent's Age.

	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Less than 30 yrs	65	50.78	57.78
31 to 40 yrs	35	27.34	77.78
41 to 50 yrs	20	15.63	93.41
More than 51 yrs	8	6.25	100
	128	100	

Table III: Respondent's marital status.

	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Married	75	58.59	58.59
Single	53	41.41	100
	128	100	

Table IV: Respondent's qualification.

	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Graduation	45	35.15	35.15
Masters	73	57.03	92.18
MS/M.phil	10	7.81	100.0
PhD	0	0	
	128	100	

Table V: Respondent's nature of the job contract.

	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Permanent	89	69.53	69.53
Temporary	39	30.47	100
	128	100	

Table VI: Respondent's working position.

	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Officer	45	35.16	35.16
Supervisor	42	32.81	67.97
Assistant manager	25	19.53	87.5
Manager	16	12.5	100
	128	100	

Table VII: Respondent's income range.

	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Less than 20,000	29	22.66	22.66
21,000 to 40,000	32	25.00	47.66
41,000 to 60,000	41	32.03	79.69
More than 60,000	26	20.31	100
	128	100	

Table VIII: Respondent's Area of Responsibilities.

	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Customer services	24	18.75	18.75
Administration	33	25.78	44.53
Sales & Distribution	24	18.75	63.28
Planning &	16	12.50	75.78
Implementation	14	10.94	86.72
Finance department	11	8.59	95.31
Trade Marketing	6	4.69	100
Others			
	128	100	

Table IX: Respondent's working experience in the organization.

	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Less than 5 yrs	25	19.53	19.53
5 to 10 yrs	55	42.97	62.50
11 to 15 yrs	35	27.34	89.84
More than 15 yrs	13	10.16	100
	128	100	

GENERAL FINDINGS:

Does your educational qualification suits your job?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent

Valid	S.Agree	55	42.97	42.97	42.97
	Agree	42	32.81	32.81	75.28
	Some How	15	11.72	11.72	87.00
	Disagree	11	8.59	8.59	95.59
	S.Disagree	5	3.91	3.91	100
	Total	128	100	100	

The above table shows that 42.97% Strongly agreed, 32.81% agreed, 11.72 somehow agreed that their qualification suits with their job. Only 8.59% disagreed, 3.91% strongly disagreed and said that their educational qualification does not suit with their job which cause stress to them.

Lack of administrative support:

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	S.Agree	25	19.53	19.53	19.53
	Agree	42	32.81	32.81	52.34
	Some How	33	25.78	25.78	78.12
	Disagree	17	13.28	13.28	91.40
	S.Disagree	11	8.59	8.59	100
	Total	128	100	100	

From the above table it is clear that lack of administrative support causes stress and the performance of the respondent decreases as the 19.53% respondent were strongly agreed, 32.81% were agreed and 25.78% were somehow agreed that lack of administrative support cause stress which in turns decrease their performance. 13.28% were disagreed and only 8.59% were strongly disagreed with that.

Work overload and time pressure:

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	S.Agree	27	21.09	21.09	21.09
	Agree	46	35.94	35.94	57.03
	Some How	23	17.97	17.97	75.00
	Disagree	19	14.84	14.84	89.84
	S.Disagree	12	9.37	9.37	100
	Total	128	100	100	

The results are clearly indicating that significant majority of respondent were agreed(21.09% were strongly agreed, 35.94% were agreed and 17.97% were somehow agreed) that work overload and time pressure is a big source of stress in their job and also leads towards decreased performance. While 14.94% were disagreed and 9.37% strongly disagreed.

Problematic Customer relations:

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	S.Agree	35	27.34	27.34	27.34
	Agree	28	21.87	21.87	49.21
	Some How	37	28.91	28.91	78.12
	Disagree	18	14.06	14.06	92.18

S.Disagree	10	7.81	7.81	100
Total	128	100	100	

Due to operational risk a banker often face problematic customer relations which cause stress. 27.34% were strongly agreed, 21.87 % were agreed and 28.91% were somehow agreed that problematic customer relations caused stress and the performance of the respondent decreased. 14.06 % were disagreeing and only 7.81% strongly disagreed with that.

Coworkers Relation:

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid S.Agree	58	45.31	45.31	45.31
Agree	36	28.13	28.13	73.44
Some How	19	14.85	14.85	88.29
Disagree	11	8.59	8.59	96.88
S.Disagree	4	3.13	3.13	100
Total	128	100	100	

The above table clearly demonstrates that coworker's relations caused stress to employees working in bank. 45.31% respondent were strongly agreed, 28.1% agreed and 14.85 % were somehow agreed that the lack of social support from colleagues and poor interpersonal relations cause stress and they feel inconvenient to work with them and hence their performance decreased. Only 3.13% were disagreed with it.

Riskiness of job:

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid S.Agree	33	25.78	25.78	25.78
Agree	27	21.09	21.09	46.87
Some How	39	30.47	30.47	77.34
Disagree	19	14.84	14.84	92.18
S.Disagree	10	7.81	7.81	100
Total	128	100	100	

As in bank there is operational risk is involved while employees are working. Due to online system of transactions employees have to be careful while entering account details especially the amount of the transaction. Because once the data entered the transaction becomes online countrywide, thus any negligent act leads towards penalty to employees. So this operational risk becomes a constituent of stress in employees working in bank as in above table majority of the respondents agreed that riskiness of the job cause stress and ultimately decrease their performance.

Family and work life Relation:

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid S.Agree	23	17.97	17.97	17.97
Agree	35	27.34	27.34	45.31
Some How	47	36.72	36.72	82.03
Disagree	16	12.50	12.50	94.53
S.Disagree	7	5.47	5.47	100
Total	128	100	100	

Due to work over load the bankers have to spend extra time apart from their working hours so they are unable to manage work and family life properly that causes stress in them as the significant majority of respondents were

agreed with that (17.97% were strongly agreed, 27.34% were agreed and 36.72% were somehow agreed). 12.5% respondents were disagreed and 5.47% were strongly disagreed with that.

Overall job stress:

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	S.Agree	52	40.62	40.62	40.62
	Agree	43	33.59	33.59	74.21
	Some How	17	13.81	13.81	88.02
	Disagree	9	7.03	7.03	95.05
	S.Disagree	7	5.47	5.47	100
	Total	128	100	100	

The above table demonstrates that 40.62% respondents were strongly agreed that their job is stressful, 33.59% were agreed and 13.81% were somehow agreed with that. Only 7.03% were disagreed and 5.47% were strongly disagreed and said their job is not stressful.

What you Feel while you are on your job? (Tick one):

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Aggressive and depressed	30	23.44	23.44	23.44
Lazy boredom and headache	18	14.06	14.06	37.50
Deficiency in work	23	17.97	17.97	55.47
You do the best possible job	12	9.38	9.38	64.85
Motivated, productive and creative.	16	12.50	12.50	77.35
Better handle the situation	9	7.03	7.03	84.38
Enjoy work	13	10.16	10.16	94.54
Stay calm	7	5.47	5.47	100
Total	128	100	100	

The above table shows what the respondents feeling while they were on their job. The data indicated that 23.44 % of the respondents feel depression and become aggressive.14.1% become lazy and suffered from headache. The 17.97 % of the respondents did feel deficiency in work. So an enormous majority did feel stress and their performance decreased. Only 9.38 % respondents do their best possible under stress. 12.50 % become motivated and more productive in stressed environment. It was further envisaged from data that 7.03% respondents better handle the situation under stress,10.16% Enjoy work and 7 % respondents Stay calm and said that they never felt stress. The table of correlation analysis shows the relationships of all the variables.

Correlation analysis.

		Does your educational qualification suits your job?	Lack of administrative support	Work overload and time pressure	Problematic Customer relations	Coworkers Relation	Riskiness of job	Family and work life Relation	Overall job stress
Does your educational qualification suits your job?	Pearson Correlation	1	.912**	.907**	.913**	.965**	.914**	.925**	.977**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	128	128	128	128	128	128	128	128
Lack of administrative support	Pearson Correlation	.912**	1	.974**	.961**	.913**	.954**	.952**	.911**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	128	128	128	128	128	128	128	128
Work overload and time pressure	Pearson Correlation	.907**	.974**	1	.949**	.913**	.945**	.937**	.909**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	128	128	128	128	128	128	128	128
Problematic Customer relations	Pearson Correlation	.913**	.961**	.949**	1	.919**	.986**	.945**	.917**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000		.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	128	128	128	128	128	128	128	128
Coworkers Relation	Pearson Correlation	.965**	.913**	.913**	.919**	1	.918**	.933**	.957**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000		.000	.000	.000
	N	128	128	128	128	128	128	128	128
Riskiness of job	Pearson Correlation	.914**	.954**	.945**	.986**	.918**	1	.954**	.917**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000		.000	.000
	N	128	128	128	128	128	128	128	128
Family and work life Relation	Pearson Correlation	.925**	.952**	.937**	.945**	.933**	.954**	1	.932**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000		.000
	N	128	128	128	128	128	128	128	128
Overall job stress	Pearson Correlation	.977**	.911**	.909**	.917**	.957**	.917**	.932**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	128	128	128	128	128	128	128	128

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The above table confirms that all job stress attributes (educational background, lack of administrative support, work overload and time pressure, riskiness of job, problematic customer relations, co-worker relations and family & work life relations) are positively associated with overall job stress. Employees education shows the highest positive correlation ($r = .977$) with job stress and Co-worker relations the second highly positive correlation ($r = .957$) with job stress, followed by riskiness of job ($r = .917$), lack of administrative support ($r = .911$), problematic customer relations ($r = .917$), family and work life relations ($r = .932$) all have positive association with job stress. Work overload and time pressure reveals the least but positive correlation ($r = .909$) with job stress.

Regression:

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.980 ^a	.961	.960	.229

The value of R in the table is .980, and R square is .961. The value of R shows significantly positive relationship between variables (educational background, lack of administrative support, work overload, riskiness of job, problematic customer relations, co-worker relations, family and work life relations) and overall job stress. The value of R square shows that model 1 explains 96% variance in overall job stress.

Conclusion:

Greater part of the employees of Mobile phone companies felt that their job is stress full and that stress in return reduces their performance. Work overload, risky job and poor co-worker relations were the major donor to job stress in Mobile phone companies employees. Due to work overload and time pressure the Mobile phone Company's employees are not capable to handle work life with family life which cause some serious social problems. Therefore the overstressed job decreases employee performance and perhaps a chief contributor to employee dissatisfaction. All these factors create a lot of problems for the employee and they indulged into mental depression, drinking, smoking, heart disease, brain tumor and many other problems. To fulfill their job requirements workers use unfair means such as telling a lie, work shirking, fraud and lame excuses. Proper strategies should be made regarding working hours, interpersonal relationships and supervision of Mobile phone companies to reduce stress and to better manage the performance of employees in Mobile phone companies.

References:

- AIS. (2012, may 21). *EFFECTS OF STRESS*. Retrieved June 24, 2012, from American Institute of Stress: www.stress.org/topic-effects.htm
- Farrell, b. G. (2005). *Reconciling Labour Flexibility with Social Cohesion: Facing the ...*, Volume 71. Strasbourg Cedex: Council of Europe Publishing.
- Houtman, I. L. (2007). Work-related stress. *European Foundation for the Improvement of Living and Working Conditions, Wyattville Road, Loughlinstown, Dublin 18, Ireland*. - Tel: (+353 1) 204 31 00 - Fax: 282 42 09 / 282 64 56, 4.
- Howard, N. (2012). The Effects of Stress on Business Employees and Programs Offered by Employers to Manage Stress.
- HSE, H. a. (2009). *How to deal with stress*. Retrieved 07 07, 2012, from BusinesslinK: www.businesslink.gov.uk › ... › Managing the welfare of people
- Ismail, T. T.-H. (2011). Identifying Work-Related Stress among Employees in the Malaysian Financial Sector. *Jalan Universiti, Bandar Sunwa 46150, Petaling Jaya, Selangor, Malaysia waltert@sunway.edu.my* , 1.
- Jeanne B, S. (2011). *Corrections Foundations for the future 2nd edition*. 270 Madison Avenue, New York: Taylor & Francis Amazon.com.
- Jeffrey A. Kottler, D. D. (2011). *Stress Management and Prevention: Applications to Daily Life*. New York: Taylor & Francis Group 711 Third Avenue, New York.
- Junior, A. (2008). *Dispatch/Telecommunications*. Retrieved July 4, 2012, from [newstudentcenter.ja.org](http://newstudentcenter.ja.org/newstudentcenter.ja.org/Careers/Research/.../Telecommunications.asp): newstudentcenter.ja.org/Careers/Research/.../Telecommunications.asp.
- Kaila, H. L. (2005). *Human Resource Management, Volume 2*. Delhi: Kalpaz Publications C-30, Satyawati Nagar, Delhi India. .
- Karimi, R. (2011). Reduce Job stress in Organizations: Role of Locus of Control . *International Journal of Business and Social Science* , 234.
- Leblebici. (2012). IMPACT OF WORKPLACE QUALITY ON EMPLOYEE'S PRODUCTIVITY: CASE STUDY OF A BANK IN TURKEY. *Journal of Business, Economics & Finance*, 38.
- Leblebici, D. (2012). IMPACT OF WORKPLACE QUALITY ON EMPLOYEE'S PRODUCTIVITY: CASE STUDY OF A BANK IN TURKEY. *Journal of Business, Economics & Finance (2012), Vol.1 (1)* , 38.
- Leka, S. (2003). Work Organization & Stress. *Publications of the world Health Organization 20 Appia, 1211 Geneva 27, Switserzerland*, 9.
- MANJULA, C. (2007). A Study on Personality Factors Causing Stress among School Teachers . *LANGUAGE IN INDIA Strength for Today and Bright Hope for Tomorrow Volume 12 : 2 February 2012*, 7 & 8.
- Medibank. (2008). The Cost of Workplace Stress in Australia. *Medibank Private and Workplace Health*, www.medibank.com.au/client/.../pdfs/the-cost-of-workplace-stress.pdf, 5.
- Perrewe, P. L. (2004). *Emotional and Physiological Processes and Positive Intervention Strategies*. New York-Paris-Tokyo: Emerald Group Publishing Amazon.com.
- Rahim, S. H. (2010). Emotional Intelligence and Stress: An Analytical Study of Pakistan Banks. *International Journal of Trade, Economics and Finance, Vol. 1, No. 2*, 194.

S Michie, D. S. (2002). *CAUSES AND MANAGEMENT OF STRESS AT WORK*. Retrieved July 03, 2012, from OCCUPATIONAL & ENVIRONMENTAL STRESS: www.oem.bmj.com/content/59/1/67.full

Salami, A. ., (2010). Impact of Job Stress on Managers' Performance. *European Journal of Scientific Research* © EuroJournals Publishing, Inc. 2010 <http://www.eurojournals.com/ejsr.htm>, 253.

Samuel Obino Mokaya, J. W. (2012). Effects of Workplace Recreation on Employee Performance The Case of Kenya Utalii College. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science* , 177.

SINHA. (2012). Genesis, Effect and Solutions to stress due to Job-insecurity A Brief Psychological Review. www.princeton.edu/~sinha/Psychology_term_paper.pdf, 2.

Thaman, A. (2012, 03 01). *Effect Of Stress On Decision Making Revealed In A Study*. Retrieved 07 07, 2012, from Themedguru: www.themedguru.com/.../effect-stress-decision-making

THE IMPACT OF STRESS ON THE EMPLOYEES INVOLVED IN HOSPITALITY BUSINESS. (n.d).

Warren, B. (2007). *Suffering the Slings and Arrows of Outrageous Fortune: International Perspectives on Stress, Laughter, and Depression* . New York: Rodopi B.V., Amsterdam- New York, NY 2007.

WebMD. (2009, April 22). *What Causes Job Stress?* Retrieved July 03, 2012, from WebMD: www.webmd.com/mental.../managing-job-stress-what-causes-job-stre